

Loyalty from Prenatal Care to Delivery: Managing Expectations

Kimberly Liggins Fontenot DNP, CNM, MBA --- Dana N. Rutledge, PhD, RN, Project Chair

Background

In the 1980s, a metropolitan county hospital in southern CA had 100 deliveries per day
Medical laws changed
Now, 100 deliveries per month
Much higher capacity

Statement of Problem

Low LDR utilization
~\$1500/delivery is lost
Safety at risk with missing medical histories
Lack of continuity of care
Patient satisfaction r/t expectations of care

Outcome Goals

Increase patient loyalty

- 90% delivery rate in 6 months
- 5-10% ↓ in all missed appointments

Process Outcomes

Information sharing

- Prenatal teaching
- Laborist Model

Missed appointment follow up
Hospital tour scheduled
Post partum appointment made

Run Chart for Missed Appointment Rates

Revised Theoretical Framework

Critical Outcomes

New and return missed appointments
Delivery rate
Post-partum missed appointments
All rates indicate how well patients are being processed through prenatal care system

Missed Appointments

Limitations

- Limited time for project
- Limited scope- CNM activity focused
- Still in process
- Multiple events can also impact outcomes (e.g., new EHR, lack of staffing, staff changes)

Progress Made

- Opening up communication lines between staff across departments
- Gain of decreasing missed appointment rates
- Increase in rates of deliveries from CNM clinic

